

Digital Care Gap at Home – Digital Housekeeping & Gender

Social context

- The home is not a gender-neutral space. It is deeply associated with femininity – intimacy, love, and family – and culturally framed as the counterpart to paid labor outside the home.
- Gender Care Gap is a well-known phenomenon:

For women:

The home remains the central site of unpaid and often undervalued domestic and care work, including childcare, eldercare, household chores, emotional support, and the organization of everyday family life.

For men:

The home is more often a space of leisure. Their time at home typically involves entertainment (TV, internet, gaming), or repairs – activities that are culturally associated with relaxation or hobbies.

- While the home is often idealized as a place of safety, it is statistically the most dangerous place for women and children. Domestic violence – primarily perpetrated by men – affects mostly women and is on the rise.

Why is digital housekeeping relevant?

More and more households are integrating digital technologies – through smart home systems, remote work setups, digital energy management, and household administration.

Digital housekeeping refers to the often invisible work required to manage and maintain digital infrastructures at home. It includes decision-making, installation, troubleshooting, data organization, and the seamless integration of these technologies into everyday life.

As homes become more digitalized, the scope and complexity of digital housekeeping tasks increase accordingly.

Digital housekeeping is gendered

In different-sex households, men typically act as the “tech gurus” who manage and control smart home systems and devices.

Smart technologies are often linked to traditionally male-coded domains – such as energy management, home security, and leisure activities like entertainment.

Women frequently take a more passive role in digital decision-making due to limited financial autonomy, lack of time, lower digital confidence, or restricted access to relevant skills training.

What are the impacts?

1 Reinforcing Gender Inequality:

Women’s limited involvement in digital household decisions perpetuates existing gender gaps in both care work and technology-related domains.

2 Masculinization of Digital Labor:

Digital housekeeping is often framed as a hobby or personal interest for men, enabling skill accumulation and fostering male-dominated networks and exchanges around smart technologies – both online and offline.

3 Not less work for:

While digital housekeeping increases men’s responsibilities, it rarely leads to a redistribution of traditional housework and caregiving tasks, which continue to fall disproportionately on women.

4 Risk of Surveillance and Power Abuse:

The person who controls the tech, typically the male “guru” – can monitor and manage the behavior of other household members. This creates new power hierarchies between partners, parents and children, tenants and landlords or employers and domestic workers, reinforcing inequalities and enabling forms of surveillance-based control.

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This Fact Sheet is part of the SMARTUP Project: *Smart(ening up the modern) home – Redesigning power dynamics through domestic space digitalisation*. The German, Czech, and Polish consortiums for this CHANSE project are funded by the German Ministry of Education and Research [grant number: 01UX2209], the Czech Academy of Sciences [grant number: 796], and the National Science Centre in Poland [grant number: 2021/03/Y/HS6/00250], respectively.

Consortium: Czech Academy of Sciences (CZ), Aalto University (FI), University of Göttingen (DE), University of Lodz (PL), Cardiff University (UK). © 2024 Institute of Sociology CA | e-mail: socmail@soc.cas.cz | **SMARTUP website:** <https://smartup-chanse.eu/en/about-project>

Design and Layout: Reem Okasha, Cardiff University (UK).

Funding organisations:

CHANSE ERA-NET Co-fund programme, funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement no 101004509.

